



BACKGROUND

The UK construction industry is the largest consumer of natural resources estimated at 400 million tonnes and producing about 100 million tonnes of waste yearly. The volume of waste produced during construction activities and demolition in the United Kingdom accounted for 62% of total waste in 2018. Data management is one of the main challenges identified, showing gaps in data inconsistencies, reporting, collection, harmonization, accessibility, and storage.

AIM

This paper will explore about how material passport can be used to obtain information for end of service life for materials and products in construction and demolition stages which is shown in figure 1.



Figure 1- Material passport (Heinrich and Lang, 2019)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Material passports are presented as a solution with great potential to create datasets about construction materials and products in buildings. A systematic review was carried out about material passport application in building life cycle assessment and circular economy in the built environment.

DATA SOURCES

“A material passport is a qualitative and quantitative documentation of the material composition of a building, displaying materials embedded in buildings as well as showing their recycling potential and environmental impact”(Honic et al., 2019).The data sources for material passport are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Stakeholders for material passport.

Table with 5 columns: Stakeholder, Adisorn et al. (2021), Hoosain et al. (2021), Uí Chúláin et al. (2022), van Capelleveen et al. (2023). Rows include Builders, Engineer, Architects, Real Estate, Owners, Financial partners, Government, Materials suppliers, Manufacturer, External sources, Other platform users, Quality Assurance body.

MATERIAL PASSPORT

Material passport involves the whole life cycle of the materials & products as seen in figure 2.



Figure 2- Material passport (Waterman, 2022)

EXPECTED DATA FROM MATERIAL PASSPORT

The variety of data expected from material passport is shown in fig 3



DISCUSSION

- ✓ There is a need to identify the key data required by stakeholders in determining the exact data to be captured for material passport generation and universal usage and acceptance.
✓ Government should take ownership of all data's regarding buildings and be made publicly available for ease of access.
✓ Digital marketplace for secondary materials and products from building needs to be expanded to accommodate other materials and products that have residual value in them and not limited to the major waste streams like concrete, wood, glass, iron, steel, as this will help the demand and supply capacity for secondary materials.
✓ Material passport design should incorporate a financial decision tool that compares different cost benefit analysis based on use of materials and product sources.

REFERENCES

Adisorn, T., Tholen, L., & Götz, T. (2021). Towards a Digital Product Passport Fit for Contributing to a Circular Economy. Energies, 14, 2289.
Heinrich, M., & Lang, W. (2019). Materials Passports - Best Practice - Innovative Solutions for a Transition to a Circular Economy in the Built Environment.
Hoosain, M. S., Paul, B. S., Raza, S. M., & Ramakrishna, S. (2021). Material Passports and Circular Economy. In L. Liu & S. Ramakrishna (Eds.), An Introduction to Circular Economy (pp. 131-158). Springer Singapore.
Uí Chúláin, C., McGetrick, P. J., & Harte, A. M. (2022). Traceability protocols for timber construction materials and products.
van Capelleveen, G., Vegter, D., Olthaar, M., & van Hillegersberg, J. (2023). The anatomy of a passport for the circular economy: a conceptual definition, vision and structured literature review. Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances, 17.